

Megasporocarps and microsporocarps were handpicked, mixed at a 1:2 ratio, and sterilized for spore germination under *in vitro* conditions.

Spores were centrally placed in petri dishes containing sterile NO₃ solid medium. We added 2-3 ml of vitamins (ascorbic acid, vitamin B1, pantothenic acid, nicotinic acid, and riboflavin, each at 25 ppm) and incubated the plates under 1500-2000 lux light.

All vitamins tested stimulated megaspore germination (Table 1). Germination and fertilization were higher with nicotinic acid and riboflavin.

In a survival study, dried sporocarps that had been stored in burlap bags for 1, 2, and 3 yr were presoaked separately for 12 h in growth regulator GA₃ and systemic fungicide carbendazim (both at 100 ppm). These were released into soil extract medium. Another batch of sporocarps was presoaked in a combined solution before release.

Some sporelings developed from all three storage groups (Table 2). Spores stored for 1 yr survived better than older spores, regardless of the soaking solution. Spores from treated sporocarps had improved germination. □

Table 1. Effect of vitamins on *A. microphylla* spore fertilization.

Vitamins (25 ppm)	Fertilization (% emerged sporelings)	Increase (%) over control
Ascorbic acid	49.68	38.19
Vitamin B1	54.46	51.49
Pantothenic acid	56.88	58.22
Nicotinic acid	65.96	83.48
Riboflavin	63.75	77.33
Control	35.95	
CV	24.01	

Table 2. Studies on the viability of frond-based spore inoculum of *A. microphylla* stored in burlap bags.

Presoaking solution (100 ppm)	Sporelings that emerged ^a (no./tub)		
	1 yr old	2 yr old	3 yr old
GA ₃	217.50	13.50	-
Carbendazim	75.50	19.00	2.50
GA ₃ + carbendazim	220.50	3.50	0.50
Control	146.00	7.00	2.50
CV	12.21		

^aEach 5-g dried spore inoculum used 300 megasporocarps. This was constant for each treatment tested.

Use of rice straw under submerged conditions

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We studied the feasibility of applying fresh rice straw under submerged conditions to rice variety Jaya during the 1983 kharif (monsoon) and 1984 wet season (WS).

Soil was loamy with pH 7.8, 0.43% organic C. Available NPK were 181, 6.6, and 152 kg/ha. We incorporated 5 and 10 t straw with and without additional N. A uniform dressing of 26 kg P and 49 kg

K/ha was applied. Straw was incorporated 21 d before transplanting.

Grain and straw yields increased significantly with rice straw incorporation (Table 1). Yield and N uptake were best with 5 t rice straw and 100 kg N/ha applied together.

We examined N mineralization rate in normal (pH 7.8) and sodic (pH 10.1) soils under submerged conditions in the laboratory. Ammoniacal N content was less in sodic than in normal soil (Table 2). This was related to soil organic C content.

In both soils, N content increased up to 30 d, then decreased. Adding rice straw accelerated the mineralization rate. Maximum NH₄-N content (53.5 ppm) was with 200 ppm fertilizer N and 10 t rice straw/ha. □

Table 1. Effect of N fertilizer and rice straw on yield and N uptake by rice plants.

Treatment	1983				1984			
	Yield (t/ha)		N uptake (kg/ha)		Yield (t/ha)		N uptake (kg/ha)	
	Grain	Straw	Grain	Straw	Grain	Straw	Grain	Straw
Control	2.3	4.6	36.7	28.2	2.5	4.2	33.1	25.6
5 t rice straw	3.3	5.7	43.3	35.1	3.0	4.8	39.7	29.9
10 t rice straw	3.3	5.8	44.0	36.6	3.1	5.0	41.0	31.6
100 kg N (urea)	4.1	7.1	55.3	46.6	3.8	6.4	51.2	41.6
100 kg N (urea) + 5 t rice straw	4.4	7.6	59.6	50.2	4.1	7.0	55.7	46.2
100 kg N (urea) + 10 t rice straw	4.4	7.7	60.0	50.6	4.1	7.1	56.1	46.9
LSD (0.05)	0.2	0.4	3.0	2.8	0.2	0.4	2.6	2.5

Table 2. Effect of rice straw on NH₄-N release under submerged condition in normal and sodic soils.

Treatment	NH ₄ -N (ppm)							
	Normal soil				Sodic soil			
	15 d	30 d	45 d	60 d	15 d	30 d	45 d	60 d
Control	10.8	12.1	9.1	5.2	8.0	9.4	5.3	3.0
Rice straw (10 t/ha)	13.7	14.0	9.8	5.6	11.1	13.7	7.6	3.7
Fertilizer N (200 ppm)	38.0	43.3	28.4	11.1	13.7	26.4	15.4	5.7
Fertilizer N (200 ppm) + rice straw (10 t/ha)	45.8	53.5	35.0	12.6	26.6	31.2	18.8	6.1
Mean	27.07	30.72	20.57	8.62	17.35	20.17	11.77	4.62

Integrated pest management—diseases

Managing rice sheath blight (ShB) using fungal antagonists and organic amendments

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We evaluated the efficacy of two antagonistic fungi (*Trichoderma longibrachiatum* [Tl] and *Gliocladium virens* [Gv]) and two organic manures (*Gliricidia maculata* leaves and *Azadirachta indica* [neem] cake), both individually and combined, to control ShB caused by *Rhizoctonia solani*.